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Kofi Annan: A Portrait of African Diplomat in the United Nations, 1938 – 2018

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Abstract

Kofi Annan, a Ghanaian, African, social activist, erudite scholar, Keynesian Economist, International Political Economist, International Civil Servant, renowned diplomat, UN 7th Secretary General, a good manager of men and material and an elite, was born on the 8th of April 1938 in Kumasi, in modern day Ghana. He traveled the intellectual world and bagged academic degrees, Nobel Prizes and honours. Annan joined the United Nations in 1962, through the stalling ranks to become the 7th Secretary General of the global body in September 1997. He remained the first in Sub-Saharan Africa and second in African continent to occupy that exalted office. He retired from the United Nations in December 2006, died in August 2018 and buried in September 2018 at the Accra International Conference Centre. This paper is a brief biographical account of which encapsulates the life and times of this dramatic persona, Kofi Atta Annan.

Introduction

His Excellency, Sir Kofi Annan, was a child of destiny. He was born on April 8, 1938, to the family of Henry Reginald and Victoria Annan. Kofi grew up to be a great and renowned African diplomat, politician, statesman, and mentor. As a distinguished member of the black race, Kofi was pragmatic and a disciplined African who appreciated and adhered to the core values and norms of Africa.

He attended schools in Ghana before leaving for Student Leadership and Scholarship Program. In 1958, Kofi was elected Vice President of the Ghana National Student Union. This position marked the genesis of his leadership, which culminated in his becoming Secretary General of the United Nations in 1997.

During his tenure as the Secretary General of this global body, Kofi displayed a high sense of dynamism and superlative leadership, anchored in humility and transparency. As the Secretary General, he introduced many reforms and innovations into the administrative machinery of the United Nations, some of which clashed with the

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interests of the major world powers. He made various structural changes at the UN Secretariat and introduced the Millennium Development Goals to encourage and promote the development of developing countries and uplift the living conditions of the global citizenry.¹

In line with the primary objective of the UN—the promotion and maintenance of international peace and security—Kofi introduced the Historic Peace Agenda Initiative and spearheaded its adoption and implementation by all member states of the United Nations. In order to contain the high level of human rights violations, genocide, unlawful imprisonment, and suppression of opposition by an autocratic government, which was one of the challenges to the principles of the United Nations, Kofi initiated the 'Responsibility to Protect' to enable the UN to intervene in these situations to halt the crimes against humanity.

Kofi encouraged the African Union not to recognise military and authoritarian regimes, thereby encouraging the growth and institutionalisation of democracy and representative government in Africa. During his tenure as the Chief Scribe of the global body, he championed the settlement of disputes between Israel and its Arab neighbours, Nigeria and Cameroon over Bakassi, Rwanda and Somalia over Darfur, Serbia and Bosnia, East Timor, and Indonesia, among others.²

Kofi Annan: Birth, Parentage, Educational and Diplomatic Training

Kofi Annan was born on April 8, 1938, to the family of Henry Reginald Annan and Victoria Annan in Kumasi, the capital of the inland ancient kingdom of Asante in the Gold Coast (now Ghana). Kofi's early education was affected by the itinerant nature of his father's profession. His father moved from district to district in all parts of Ghana because of his posting or redeployment as the district manager of UAC. The obvious impact of this situation was that Kofi had to wait until he turned fifteen before enrolling in school. In 1953, Kofi enrolled in Mfantisipin Academic School, an elite boarding school located in the hilly area of the town of Cape Coast. While passing out six years later, Kofi took the exams and joined the Kumasi Institute of Science and Technology. At the institute, Kofi joined students' activism and unionism and was subsequently selected as the institute representative at Ghana's student union in his first year. His personality, ideas, and zeal to create an enabling environment for better living conditions for his fellow students got him elected as the vice president of the Ghana National Union in his second year at Kumasi Institute.³

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Kofi, regardless of peer pressure and radicalism that characterised student unionism in Ghana and other states in Africa, showed modesty, true character, and extraordinary leadership qualities, which earned him the Ford Foundation Foreign Student Scholarship to further his studies at Macalester College in St. Paul, Minnesota, United States of America. He came out with a Bachelor of Science Degree in Economics.

Diplomatic Training

At graduation from Macalester College, Kofi Annan enrolled in the Graduate Institute of International Affairs in Geneva, and the tuition fee was paid by the Carnegie Endowment Foundation. The institute was established in 1927, during the early years of the League of Nations, mainly to train graduate students in the management of international affairs. At the Graduate Institute, Kofi studied and bagged a master degree in international political economy in 1972. In that year, Kofi Annan went for another one-year postgraduate programme at the Massachusetts Institute for Technology, Boston, United States, and earned a Master of Science degree in international management.⁴

Early Occupational Life and Journey through the United Nations System

Kofi Annan started his occupational career at the New York office of Pillsbury, a Minneapolis company, and later joined the United Nations Specialised Agency-World Health Organisation in 1962. It was while in Geneva that he enrolled in the Institute of International Studies. In 1965, Kofi Annan was promoted to the rank of an administrative officer and redeployed to the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (ECA). That redeployment brought Kofi Annan closer to the engine room of the United Nations and the Organisation of African Unity. Kofi worked at the ECA, Addis Ababa for seven years before leaving for further academic studies in 1972.⁵ On completion of his Master's Degree in International Political Economy, he was redeployed back to Geneva as a UN Senior Administrative Officer. In 1973, Kofi Annan was assigned a relief duty with the UN Emergency Peace Keeping Force in Egypt and later moved to the Middle East to oversee the Egyptian-Israeli ceasefire in the Sinai Peninsula as the head of civilian staff working with the UN forces. Three months later, Kofi Annan moved to Ismailia, a town on the Suez Canal, for another peacekeeping deal.

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When he returned in 1974, Kofi made an abrupt change of career. He left the UN and accepted the post of managing director of the Ghana Tourist Agency. In Ghana, military dictatorship and bureaucratic bottlenecks made his new assignment very tedious and difficult. Out of frustration, he returned to the United Nations in 1976, and he was posted to the Personnel Department of the UN Secretariat in New York.⁶

In 1980, Kofi Annan became the head of personnel at the UN Commission for Refugees in Geneva, and in 1983, he was redeployed as the Director of Administrative Services at the UN Secretariat. During the era of Perez De Cuellar as UN Secretary General, Kofi Annan was promoted to head of the personnel, budget, and management directorate. In 1987, Kofi Annan was appointed assistant under the Secretary General in charge of human resources. During the Gulf War in 1990/1991, Kofi Annan was redeployed to join the UNM Diplomatic Team to persuade Saddam Hussein to let go of hundreds of UN workers that were held hostage. In 1992, Kofi Annan was promoted to the rank of deputy under the Secretary General in charge of peacekeeping operations.⁷

Kofi Annan's Emergence as the UN Secretary General

A year before the end of Boutros Ghali's tenure, many controversies loomed in the office of the UN Secretary General. Rumours made the rounds that it was obvious that the United States wanted to get rid of Boutros Ghali and probably wanted an African as his successor. Ghali's disagreement with the United States over peacekeeping missions in Bosnia, Serbia, Somalia, and Rwanda and the implementation of the Dayton Accord of 1995 compelled the United States to veto Boutros Ghali's second-term bid in November 1996 during the UN Security Council to nominate a new Secretary General.⁸

Almost all African states stood behind Boutros Ghali to complete African tenure at the UN apex office, but the United States veto and their hegemonic disposition forced African states to give up on Boutros Ghali and forged ahead under the aegis of the OAU, led by President Paul Biya of Cameroon, to go for a new African nomination. It was obvious from the feeders around the UN that Kofi Annan should fill the void. Africa came up with four nominations: Amara Essy, Ivory Coast Foreign Affairs Minister Hanied Algabid, Niger former Prime Minister and Secretary General of the Organisation of Islamic Conference, Ahmadu Abdullah, a nominee of Mauritania, and Kofi Annan, nominated by Ghana.⁹

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After three days of politicking and voting in the Security Council without a winner, three other African candidates led by Amara Essy withdrew their candidatures and proposed that the General Assembly elect Kofi Annan as Secretary General by accommodation. His emergence as the 7th Secretary General of the United Nations opened a new vista in the history of the United Nations. He is the first member of the Secretariat staff to rise to the position of Secretary General. His predecessors were either politicians, diplomats, or statesmen outside the UN Secretariat.

Kofi Annan as the UN Secretary General and the Power Politics at the UN System

Kofi Annan's emergence as the UN's Secretary General was a result of a crisis that rocked the global body. He assumed office as the UN Secretary General on January 2, 1997. According to records, Kofi Annan was the 7th person to occupy the enviable office, the 2nd African Secretary General of the UN, and the first to emerge from the ranks of the UN Secretariat. Before becoming the Chief Scribe, he served under four Secretary Generals of the United Nations: U-Thant of Burma, Kurt Waldheim of Austria, Javier Perez de Cueller of Peru, and Boutros Ghali of Egypt.

At this point, his long years of service in the UN system, backed up by his experience, must have prepared him for the nature of his job, which provided the flame of a would-be statesman with no military or political power or will to enforce his decisions. His predecessors, except Dag Hammarskjold of Sweden, have wrestled with intractable problems and moods of frustration as the major world powers want the Secretary General to act their scripts. In the light of these realities, Kofi Annan did not want to dwell on the pitfalls of his new job or the difficulty of measuring up to Hammarskjold. He knew he had to approach it with the right spirit. He knew he was presiding over a weakened United Nations, which trust is yet to recover from the Cold War and post-Cold War crises that have turned Eastern Europe into an array of political disintegration, ethnicity, and irredentism. The wound of the first Gulf War was still fresh, and the UN has been heavily criticised for his poor involvement. Kofi Annan knew he must use his diplomatic skills to put things right and stay different from his predecessors. He may not march with their intellectual power, but he must be polite, much kinder, more understanding, and work more effortlessly to inject fresh air and new spirit into the organisation to deal with some challenges.

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Kofi Anan Leadership, Policies and Reforms at the United Nations

Kofi Anan started reforms in the United Nations six months after his resumption of office. He set up an agenda for better resource management and coordination across the entire UN system, as well as the promotion of human rights and peacekeeping missions.

Kofi Anan first proposed administrative reforms, reducing administrative costs to 25% of the UN budget. He overhauled the public relations directorate, connected all the UN Permanent Missions, and enhanced internal communication and administration with member states and non-governmental organisations. Anan, in order to instill more confidence and commitment among member states, instituted bureaucratic reforms by merging many departments for stronger inter-body coordination and resource mobilization. Anan introduced a single-flag visibility system and encouraged all UN agencies to use one common platform called the UN House under one flag and shared services.

In order to lessen the work load in the office of the Secretary General, Kofi Anan created the office of the Deputy Secretary General, who represented the Secretary General in conferences and other official ceremonies and ensured the effective running of the Secretariat. Throughout his tenure, Kofi Anan displayed a transformational leadership style, which postulates that leaders influence the intellectual capacity of their staffs through modernization of working techniques, research, tactical development, and upgrading of operations. He created executive committees in areas such as peacekeeping, security, economic and social affairs, development, political and diplomatic cooperation, and humanitarian affairs. These reforms enabled this directorate to perform its duties with more confidence, collaboration, and mutual trust across Africa, Europe, Asia, and America. Kofi Anan implemented the report on management and organisational measures, which introduced a new and more effective administrative direction for the UN through the establishment of a cabinet-style body to assist him and group UN activities in accordance with the four core missions of the comprehensive reform agenda.¹⁰

Kofi Anan's priorities were anchored on human rights, the rule of law, and the Millennium Development Goals, which brought the United Nations closer to the global public by forging ties with civil societies, organised private sectors, and other global partners. He introduced a peace agenda with five core pillars in ensuring and sustaining global peace. The peace agenda led to the establishment of two inter-governmental

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bodies – the Peace Building Committee and the Human Rights Council, which made efforts towards promoting global peace. Towards this end, Kofi Anan adopted and implemented the first counter-terrorism of “Responsibility to Protect” policy. The R2P doctrine attempted to break the states' notion of sovereignty and give the UN power to take action against aggression, intervene in the internal affairs of states, and protect the fundamental human rights of individuals.¹¹ Kofi Anan also launched the Global Compact Initiative, which became the largest effort to promote cooperate social responsibility which helped in the transition to democracy in Nigeria, resolve the impasse between Iraq and the United Nations. Kofi Anan played a key and mastering role in the creation of global funds for HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and malaria. He was involved in the diplomatic processes that resolved the crisis in East Timor and granted it independence from Indonesia. He ensured Israel's withdrawal from Lebanon in 2000, effected a cessation of hostilities between Israel and Hezbollah in 2006, and mediated the settlement of the dispute between Nigeria and Cameroun over Bakassi through the implementation of the International Court of Justice ruling. He strengthened peacekeeping missions to cope with the rapid rise in conflicts across the globe.¹²

Kofi Anan and Africa

Kofi Anan was the UN Secretary General from the global south, with a good understanding of the negative effects of colonialism and imperialism. His knowledge of the dynamics in both the global north and the global south showed him what was lacking and what needed to be done. Kofi Anan believed that states in the global north have a moral obligation to assist states in the global south to develop. In this context, while scholars of the radical school preach an overthrow of the capitalist world order, Anan preached an equitable distribution of resources between the rich and the poor states of the world.

In his 2000 Millennium Report, titled “The Role of the United Nations in the 21st Century,” Anan pointed at the challenges of the distribution of wealth, the benefits of globalisation to every citizen of the world, and the role the UN should play as the global umpire. The reports posited that only a handful of states transformed their economies by themselves. The reports indicted African leaders for adopting poor policies, which informed their underdevelopment. He highlighted the methods and approaches that would ensure that humanity could mutually benefit from common wealth.¹³

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Kofi Anan played a key role in resolving conflicts in Africa. One of the conflicts that received his attention was the Nigeria-Cameroun conflict over the Bakassi Peninsula. Anan, fearing that Nigeria, with its military and civilian presence in the Bakassi Peninsula, would not accept the International Court of Justice ruling, initiated participatory leadership in solving the conflict by bringing the leaders of the two African states into negotiations. After several meetings between the two states and with the input of the International Committee set up for the resolution of the conflicts, Nigeria backed down, withdrew her military and civilian personnel from the area, and handed over the peninsula to Cameroun in 2003.¹⁴

Kofi Anan undertook a challenging role for the UN in persuading Libya to hand over the suspects of the Lockerbie bombing of 1988. On assumption of office, Kofi Anan made several trips to Libya to persuade Muammor Ghads to accept a peaceful resolution of the crisis. He met and emulated renowned international personalities, viz., the Crown Prince, Abdullah of Saudi Arabia, and Nelson Mandela of South Africa, among others, on the issue. Finally, Libya bowed to this initiative and international pressure and handed over the two suspects to face trial at the International Court of Justice.¹⁵

Also, Kofi Anan played a significant role in resolving the Darfur crisis. The crisis reminded Kofi Anan of the dangerous moment of the Rwanda genocide of 1994, when he was the UN under-Secretary General for peacekeeping missions. Anan thought that the Darfur crisis may end up as the Rwandan case, and the world will hit hard on him and the UN if he fails to do the needful. Against this backdrop, Anan made various diplomatic initiatives. First, he adopted the delegation leadership style of sending various representatives to Sudan on fact-finding missions. Some of the leaders of these delegations include the UN Under-Secretary for Humanitarian Affairs, the UN High Commissioner for Refugees, the UN Special Representatives on Human Rights Defenders, and the UN Special Envoy for Humanitarian Affairs, among others. The reports and recommendations of these delegations gave Kofi Anan first-hand information on the issue. He also paid a three-day official visit to the troubled region to meet with the Chadian and Sudanese leaders. He used to visit the internally displaced persons and refugees in the rebel-held areas in Darfur and Abeche in Chad. At the end, the two states agreed to cease fire and allow the free movement of humanitarian and relief materials to reach the displaced persons and refugees. Anan addressed an AU summit in Addis Ababa and drew up the support of African leaders to resolve the crisis.

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Again, he disputed the Sub-Saharan African Agenda, aimed at attaining lasting peace and stability in the region. At the time he left office, there had been much progress in finding a permanent solution to the Darfur crisis.¹⁶

Kofi Anan made serious efforts to rebrand Africa and change development initiatives in four key areas: education, health, food and water, security and good governance. He advocated for people's-oriented leadership attainable through democracy and the abolition of military and authoritarian regimes in Africa. Kofi Anan made an official declaration of his stance on representative government and sustaining the same in Africa when he addressed the OAU Summit in Hague in 1999. He told African leaders, most of them heading military juntas, that Africa, if it must develop, must no longer tolerate and accept, as fiat accomplished, military coups against elected governments and illegal seizure of power by military juntas, who most times act for their class and selfish interests.¹⁷

He encouraged African leaders through visits, consultancy, and other related measures to adopt democracy and place power at the disposal of their people. When the regional organisation was transformed from the Organisation of African Unity to the African Union, the body accepted Anan's ideas of refusing to recognise any government that comes to power through undemocratic means and the resolve to intervene in any African state to halt genocide and other crimes against humanity.

Though he faced challenges getting these measures implemented, Anan placed at the disposal of Africa his wealth of ideas, experience, and energy for the betterment of his continent.¹⁸

Kofi Anan and the Middle East

The Middle East has been in crisis since the United Nations partitioned the Palestinian territory into separate states for Arabs and Jews in 1947. But the Jews, after the partition, declared a state and named it Israel, forcing violent reactions from Arab states and a series of Israeli-Arab wars. Worried by the continuous crisis and inability in the region and bearing in mind the inabilities of the parties to end these conflicts, Kofi Anan proposed a major-power mechanism to enforce peace from outside. Anan assembled a group of international mediators and drafted a road map for reconciliation and peace. Anan's initiative created a better level of understanding between Israel and Palestine: the Israelis agreed to freeze their settlement programmes, and the Palestinians agreed to end

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terror attacks. The European Union and Russia ratified the plan, but the United Nations opposed it, prompting Israel to issue fourteen-point reservations to Anan's Peace Plan. However, Anan's push for peace in the Middle East continued unabated as he met several times with state leaders of the region, organisations, and civil societies.¹⁹

When Israel announced its withdrawal from Gaza, Kofi Anan seized the opportunity to bring peace to the troubled region, but George Bush's America scuttled the process courtesy of his possessiveness and imperial aggressiveness. Anan's effort was opposed when the United Nations began a campaign in the UN Security Council to break Syria's grip on Lebanon. Due to its strategic location, regional influence, and importance, a free and democratic Lebanon should have been a celebrated achievement for the UN, but Anan feared such more could damage the UN because of the speculated perception of a double standard in the Council's determination to drive Syria out of Lebanon, compared to its passive disposition towards Israel's occupation of Arab land.

Anan diplomatically pleaded with all parties—Syria, Iraq, and the United States—to pave the way for a peaceful resolution. At last, Syria agreed to withdraw, but a couple of damaging crises occurred. One Lebanese Prime Minister was assassinated in a Beirut bombing and other terrorist violence, including Hezbollah's attack on Israel and hostage-taking. This brought Hezbollah and Israel to war, with heavy casualties in northern Israel and Lebanon.²⁰

Kofi Anan worked with Lebanon and most world leaders to end the crisis, but again, the United States refused to take part, claiming to give Israel time to adhere to their agenda of total destruction of Hezbollah. The war lasted for 34 days, and the consequences took on a different dimension against the expectation of the United States. Despite the consequences of the war, Israel and the United States refused to settle for peace. Later in 2006, Kofi Anan established his commitment to resolving the Middle East crisis when The Militant Hamas Movement won the general election in Palestine. The United States and Israel rejected the result of the poll and refused to recognise the government. Kofi Anan tried to intervene, but he was shot out by the unbending will of the Americans.²¹ Until he left office, the problem was still lingering, even to this day.

Kofi Anan, Latin America, and the Caribbean

Kofi Anan knew Latin America and the Caribbean as one of the poorest regions prone to natural disasters. When he assumed office, he initiated a series of policies and

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programmes to tackle most of these issues. First, he initiated the Nairobi Framework Partnership in 2006 as a means to bolster the link between states in Latin America and the Caribbean, the private sector, and the G8. This measure was aimed at assisting the regions in implementing the Paris Agreement on Climate Change. For a continent flanked by two great oceans—the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans—the region is very vulnerable to extreme weather storms and hurricanes, causing devastating effects on the population. In view of these situations, Kofi Anan pressed forward for the full implementation of the Paris Agreement—to strengthen the global response to the threat of climate change by keeping the global temperature rise below two degrees Celsius—and made an effort to limit the temperature increment.²²

Kofi Anan took participatory leadership by insisting and encouraging the government of Costa Rica to implement the Carbon Neutrality Policy, the government of Chile to enforce efficient carbon taxes and penalties, and the government of Mexico to enforce general laws on climate change. These measures yielded effective results.

Kofi Anan took steps to address electoral violence and fraud by introducing the “Electoral Integrity Initiative” in some Latin American states. He used the initiative to share experiences, compare challenges, and strengthen measures towards electoral integrity through peaceful elections and a smooth transition to democratic governments in the region. Anan believed that elections without integrity could not produce a winner with legitimacy and public confidence. Through the electoral initiative, Anan addressed the issues of election-related violence and money politics, among other electoral vices. These initiatives yielded tremendous results, despite some challenges.²³

Kofi Anan and International Humanitarian Intervention

Kofi Anan's 35 years at the United Nations exposed him to critical issues affecting humanity, such as bad governance, hunger, poverty, diseases, etc. Most strikingly was the challenge of violations of human rights and crimes against humanity. Anan witnessed the crimes against humanity in Rwanda, Serbia, and Somalia while serving in the various keeping missions. With all these experiences, on assumption of office, he rooted many ideas for dealing with these cases. He persuades the UN Security Council to adopt the Responsibility to Protect Initiative, giving the United Nations powers to intervene in the internal affairs of a state to relieve the suffering of people and halt crimes against humanity. For Anan, the over-riding duty birthed in his Responsibility to Protect

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Initiative will enable the UN to intervene in civil wars and other conflicts that threaten international peace and security. He reaffirmed his faith in fundamental human rights. For him, these bad leaders must not hide under the cover of sovereignty to carry out gross and barbaric violations of human rights.²⁴

The principle of Responsibility to Protect met serious opposition at first, as most third-world leaders saw it as a ploy by the developed states of the West to suppress and influence their post-colonial policies. The African Union argued that such intervention can only be justified with the consent of the state concerned. Despite these oppositions from the states in the global south, Anan was not discouraged. He pressed on through advocacy, public lectures, conferences, state visits, and shuttle diplomacy to build support for the initiative.

During the United Nations Millennium Convention, Kofi Anan reiterated the need for intervention in the internal affairs of the United Nations by states on humanitarian grounds. Even at the convention, he was opposed by a fellow African, Namibia's Foreign Affairs Minister, who was the President of the UN General Assembly. Undaunted by these challenges, Kofi Anan set up an International Commission on Intervention on State Sovereignty, and the Commission came up with a report. Armed with that report, Anan went ahead, persuading member states of the UN to accept the initiative as a framework for UN global implementation. In 2005, the initiative saw the light of day as more than one hundred and fifty UN member states adopted the initiative through a resolution of the UN General Assembly, a giant step towards progress for humanity. Since then, the initiative has been tested in Libya and other states.²⁵

Kofi Anan, the Second Gulf War, and the Oil for Food Scandal

The emergence of Mr. George Bush Jr. as American President marked a phase in the era of Kofi Anan as Secretary General of the United Nations. Bush came into power on the platform of the Republican Party in January 2001, appointing Colin Powell as Secretary of State and John Negroponte as the American Ambassador to the UN. Mr. Bush and his neo-conservative advisers did nothing for the United Nations or internationalism. They were anti-UN and saw it as an affront to national sovereignty, thus treating it with contempt.

Kofi Anan's travails started immediately after the terrorist attack on the World Trade Centre and the Pentagon on September 11, 2001. As the Secretary General of the

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United Nations, Kofi Anan condemned the attack in strong terms and immediately convened an emergency meeting of the Security Council. The Security Council passed a resolution and declared the UN readiness to fight terrorism in all its ramifications.

Kofi Anan diplomatically endorsed the American position that, under the charter of the UN, the United States could awaken the inherent right to self-defence to hunt Osama Bin Laden and other terrorists. America declared its readiness to do everything possible to fight terrorism, even as he sought the cooperation of the UN and all peace-loving states in the world to track down the terrorists and bring them to justice.

When the United States started attacking some states like Afghanistan, fagging 'rogue states' and 'axis of evil' and blaming them as harbouring, aiding, and abetting international terrorism, Kofi Anan, though in support of the war against terrorism, was worried and began to call for increased protection of the civilians in Afghanistan, a call that Washington was not comfortable with. Anan's position was about the process of fighting the terrorists, giving consideration to the civilian population. His humane disposition on this matter did not go down well with the Bush administration, hence America's negative posture towards the Anan's UN.²⁶

While the war with the Taliban was going on, Bush began another war by invading Iraq for sponsoring international terrorism. Iraq was also accused of possessing weapons of mass destruction. The case of the American invasion of Iraq did not receive the backing of the UN, hence Anan's opposition to it. According to Anan, the Middle East was already in a deep crisis, and the war in Iraq will escalate the crisis in the region. He advocated for the UN's support to legitimise the mission. The American response to Anan's position was not palatable. During the 2002 UN General Assembly session, Mr. Bush condemned Anan and the United Nations as weak and unfit to maintain global peace and security, hence telling the world that America will do so for the UN. Anan attempted to abort the American invasion of Iraq by diplomatically persuading Saddam Hussein to unconditionally allow the UN inspectors to access Iraqi military installations and weapons sites. This initiative paid off, and Saddam Hussein gave in and allowed the UN inspectors into Iraq.

When America's Powell told the Security Council about their intention to invade Iraq, all members of the council voted against it, but America went ahead and started bombing Iraq. Anan was disappointed and frustrated. He was battered by Washington, and the Republicans campaigned for his resignation. His sin was his defiance in Iraq. As

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his days at the UN drew closer, most of it became combative, troublesome, and unpleasant.²⁷

Retirement

2006 was the last year of Kofi Anan in the United Nations. The American campaign of calumny, especially the oil for food scandal, made Anan an unfair victim of American hegemonic manoeuvres. Between March and April 2006, Anan came to the AU and preached unity and solidarity for Pan-Africanism, the protection of human rights, the protection and sustenance of democratic principles, and good governance. This he did in good faith and with hope for Africa.

Kofi Anan retired from the United Nations in December 2006, after a decade of meritorious service for mankind at the United Nations. His tenure represented a good attempt to make the United Nations the needed supranational and multinational body to keep the world safe and better. He was the first UN Secretary General; hence, he had American friends and colleagues as an African who understood the problems and demands of third-world countries and was married to a Swede with a fair knowledge and understanding of European norms and values. Indeed, Anan was one of the first international civil servants with a global perception and outlook.²⁸

Kofi Anan and his legacies

Kofi Anan, from birth to death, took numerous measures and initiatives to improve and better the lot of mankind. In the area of politics, Kofi Anan inculcated the consciousness in the minds and psyches of political leaders around the world that morality and dignity must be part of political leadership in order to enhance credibility and good governance. Anan championed the spread and institutionalisation of democracy across the global south; he played a good role in the transformation of the OAU into the AU and encouraged the regional body to discountenance military regimes and autocratic governments. He encouraged Nigeria to transit to democratic governance, helped resolve the 2007 post-election crisis in Kenya, and sped up the Electoral Integrity Initiative, which helped transform many dictatorial regimes in Latin America and the Caribbean.

During his tenure as the Chief Scribe of the UN, Anan showed uncommon political leadership in managing international issues.²⁹

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In the field of diplomacy, Anan was one of the best diplomats of all time. Throughout his stay in the diplomatic world, he championed the mediation and peaceful resolution of conflicts across the globe—the Balkans, Rwanda, Somalia, and Burundi, among others. He attempted to use diplomacy in the Israel-Arab Conflict and the face-off between Washington and Baghdad; though his attempt was not a resounding success, he left a footprint on the struggle.

Anan faced opposition and political enemies with respect and understanding. As a moralist and diplomat per excellence, he knew that the contemporary global order is secular; hence, tolerance and mutual understanding must be the social transmission belt that binds across ethnic, religious, and racial lines. Anan applied tact and caution in dealing with cases of sensitivity and global threat, balancing the relationship between the major powers and the developing world.³⁰ Anan was a soft-spoken advocate and diplomat. He helped resolve many conflicts in East Timor, Kosovo, etc. His diplomatic skills and finesse redefined the Secretary General's office and flourished it with prestige, honour, and dignity.

At the United Nations, he introduced many diplomatic reforms, such as the 'Peace Agenda' and Responsibility to Protect, just to mention a few. He advocated for a just international economic order where the developed states will see themselves as being obligated to help transform the developing states into the realms of development. He initiated several economic programmes and worked closely with the Economic Commission for Africa to increase the chances of African economic development. Anan introduced the Millennium Development Goals, which represented the socio-economic rights of world citizens and the basic responsibilities to their citizenry.³¹

In the intellectual sphere, despite his official engagement and busy schedules, Kofi Anan contributed immensely to the world of knowledge. He wrote many books, journals, speeches, reports, and articles. He authored some books titled 'Intervention: A Life of War and Peace', 'Pandemic: Facing Aids' and "We the People: A United Nations for the 21st Century". He also co-authored a book titled "Combating Xenophobia and Racism: The World in Transition with Dr. Nelson Mandela of South Africa. One of the most popular articles by Kofi Anan was "In Layer Freedom: Towards Development, Security and Human Rights for All." His scholarships have made a great deal of contribution to knowledge. He was given about thirty awards and titles, too numerous to mention here.

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Kofi Anan's Last Days: Concluding Remarks

Kofi Anan, on his retirement in December 2006, established The KOFFI ANAN Foundation and used it to advance his vision of a fairer, more peaceful, and prosperous world. These he did with great zeal and a spirit of statesmanship and compassion, believing that humanity has the means and capacity to deal with its problems if it exercises the needed political will. Kofi Anan took ill, and on August 8, 2018, he died and was buried on September 13, 2018 in Ghana.³²

Kofi Anan, a Ghanaian, a true son of Africa and the black race, an Octogenarian statesman, international civil servant/diplomat, and the 7th Secretary General of the United Nations, was very active and agile until his last days, pushing forward his thoughts and desire for a better humanity, encouraging the leaders and people to strive in equal measures with equal purpose, humility, dedication, and thoughtfulness to transform the world for the better. He created a lasting legacy for the present and future generations in global hope for peace, governance, and responsibility.

ENDNOTES

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